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- * PU = Public
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- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
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Table of contents

1. Summary	5
2. Introduction.....	5
2.1 Regulations and materials in focus.....	6
3. Methodology	6
3.1 Member states in focus.....	6
4. Results.....	7
4.1 Overview of existing regulatory and statutory requirements	7
4.2 Placing construction products on the market	9
4.2.1 Construction Products Regulation	10
4.2.2 European Standard (EN-standard).....	10
4.2.3 Harmonised European Standard (hEN-standard)	11
4.2.4 European Assessment Document (EAD) and European Technical Assessment (ETA)	11
4.2.5 CE marking	11
4.2.6 Other standards	11
4.2.7 Mutual recognition principle.....	11
4.3 Placing WOODCIRCLES products on the market	12
4.3.1 Fibre insulation mats.....	12
4.3.2 Fibre insulation, loose	13
4.3.3 Cross-laminated timber.....	13
4.3.4 Glued laminated timber.....	14
4.3.5 Finger-jointed lamella.....	14
5. Conclusions	15
References	15

1. Summary

This deliverable contains a comparative analysis of EU and Member State regulatory requirements in relation to demolition sites, wood-waste recycling, engineered wood products, wood fibre insulation, and building with products that incorporate recycled materials. The information which is collected in a spreadsheet that can be adapted as changes or additions occur, provides an overview and links to the documents identified. Special focus is on the possibility of placing the developed materials on the European internal market. The analysis show that use of recycled materials in construction products is part of individual strategies for a green transition of the construction sector and that incentives have recently started to be incorporated into some national building regulations. However, the varying approaches to sourcing and sorting the input material pose a challenge to obtaining the quantity and quality necessary for WOODCIRCLES' approach to re-use and recycle wood construction products. In addition, most existing product standards as well as referenced test methods are not applicable to construction products containing recycled material, either due to specific exclusions from their scope or knowledge requirements such as geographical origin, which is unlikely to be available. While this does not prevent the placement of such products on the market, it complicates the process and thus makes it more time consuming do so.

2. Introduction

The comparative analysis of the Member States' regulatory requirements seeks to identify barriers and incentives to use demolition wood as input for engineered wood products (EWP) that are placed on the market as construction products. Special focus within the value chain Figure 1) is put on the availability of demolition wood as input for EWPs based on its properties as well as the possibilities of placing the EWPs on the European market. The analysis covers not only regulations but also directives, laws, standards, and guidance issued.

FIGURE 1: VALUE CHAIN OF URBAN FOREST MATERIALS

The data is gathered in a spreadsheet and collected at two levels: 1) an overview of requirements defined at EU-level and 2) regulation and legislation specific to each member state.

As the spreadsheet is meant as a working document that can be updated and extended as regulations are revised or new regulations are introduced, it includes the latest publishing date of the listed document and a direct web-link to it, where available.

The spreadsheet is available on the WOODCIRCLES Community in Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/woodcircles>.

2.1 Regulations and materials in focus

One focus is on regulations regarding the eligibility criteria for re-use and recycling of wooden construction and demolition waste (CDW) because it impacts the quantities available as input for the products developed within WOODCIRCLES. In addition, the analysis gives an indication of the places where and the assortments in which CDW can be sourced from.

Regarding construction products, cross-laminated timber (CLT) and glued laminated timber (GLT), including the lamellae they are produced from, are in focus, as they are already sought after construction products due to their favourable properties. Wood fibre insulation products (loose-fill and mats) are also included. The overall aim is to identify present (product) standards and the possibilities of placing these products on the market, with or without CE marking.

3. Methodology

Data collection was done as a literature study and exchange of knowledge between consortium partners, industry, RTO's and universities. DTI is currently acting as Technical Secretariat for the Group of Notified Bodies under the Construction Product Regulation and input from that work is also included.

A literature review was conducted to identify existing regulations specific to the respective links of the value chain as detailed in the introduction. Due to limited availability of literature specific to the analysis, sources of information, regulation, legislation, standards, and guidance were mostly identified by key word searches and bilateral discussions relating to the value chain.

As country specific law is often governed by regulations and directives issued on EU-level, these applicable documents were also identified and listed in the respective categories. Regarding EN standards and other evaluation documents available, pertaining to construction products in focus of WOODCIRCLES, it was analysed whether the standards were harmonised and to what extent their scope covers the products developed in WOODCIRCLES.

3.1 Member states in focus

The WOODCIRCLES consortium includes the city partners Rotterdam, Tartu, and Turin. This allows for easier access and insight to the respective country's regulations. Additionally, a demonstrator will travel between these three cities within the last year of the project before it reaches its final destination at DTI (D4.7). Therefore, the focus on data collection was placed on The Netherlands, Estonia, Italy, and Denmark.

In addition to the above-mentioned locations, data was also collected from the other Member States represented in WOODCIRCLES: Austria, Finland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. Where the search for input data revealed meaningful content applicable in Member States or other European countries not represented in WOODCIRCLES (here: Norway), this information was also added.

4. Results

4.1 Overview of existing regulatory and statutory requirements

The collection of regulatory and statutory requirements in each tab of the excel spreadsheet thematically follows the WOODCIRCLES value chain as shown in the introduction (Figure 1).

The tab titled “EU” contains regulatory requirements such as the *Waste Framework Directive* that has a direct impact on the development of Member States’ own regulations and legislation. Another example on EU level is the *REACH* regulation. In contrast to the directive, this and any other regulation is directly applicable throughout the Union and overrules any contradicting national provisions. Furthermore, guidance and protocols are available that describe how to assess construction and demolition waste and define possible wood waste categories.

More extensive information is available on regulations and standards relating to construction products in general but also to specific products and their raw material. Above all, there is the *European Construction Product Regulation*¹ that establishes harmonised rules on how to express the performance of construction products in relation to their essential characteristics and on the use of CE marking on those products. Concerning engineered wood products and fibre insulation, the specific EN standards, and existing European Assessment Documents (EAD) were assessed, and their scope was reviewed. This revealed limitations in the applicability to products developed from recycled wood due to specifications such as wood species not being allowed to be mixed within a product, the need for species to be known, or recycled wood being explicitly excluded as input material in the first place (further elaboration in chapter 4.3.). However, as the limiting factors in product standards have long been known, especially in regard to strength grading of re-used and recycled timber, there has been ongoing work in the Norwegian Standardisation Body (Standard Norge), that is in the process of having standards for the evaluation of reclaimed wood under hearing².

The final use of wooden construction products in buildings is subject to Member State provision, that for structural behaviour may refer to Eurocode 5 (EN 1995-1-1 and EN 1995-1-2) with national implementation rules.

Looking at the process of material sourcing from the urban forests by means of demolition, the pilot cities have the overall same goal of separating hazardous from non-hazardous materials at the demolition site. Denmark regulates this practice in the nationwide applicable government order on waste (Affaldsbekendtgørelsen) that explicitly requires the mapping of substances of concern such as PCBs, chlorinated paraffins, PAHs, asbestos, and heavy metals before demolition starts. Italy promotes selective demolition for the removal and safe treatment of hazardous substances as well as facilitation of reuse and high-quality recycling in more general terms. In the Netherlands it is required to identify the nature of and the destination for the material recovered at a demolition site. In other countries, e.g. Spain, regulations related to demolition of buildings primarily fall under regional or municipal jurisdiction.

The process of waste wood sorting can already be implemented at the demolition site but is executed at the latest at recycling stations where the demolition material is taken to. There, it differs from country to country but also on regional or local levels how wood materials are handled. While Italian law contains the requirement to establish a sorting system for wood, it does not further specify any criteria. In contrast, the Netherlands have established nationwide sorting classes and in the UK waste wood grades have

been defined in a guidance document issued by the Wood Recyclers' Association. In Spain, sorting of wood waste may vary between local regulations and management practices, however, wood treated with hazardous chemicals is not seen as suitable for recycling in any case. These three examples are detailed below in Table 1.

In Denmark, at a minimum, it is required by law to differentiate between impregnated and not-impregnated wood waste because impregnated wood waste must be incinerated unless a specific evaluation shows that it is suitable for either landfill or re-utilisation. Any further specifications on sorting are determined by guidance on regional and local level and it is possible for buyers to influence the sorting criteria according to their needs.

TABLE 1: EXAMPLES OF WASTE WOOD SORTING GRADES IN THE NETHERLANDS, UNITED KINGDOM AND SPAIN

Examples of waste wood sorting	Sorting grade	Definition of grade (and indication for use)
The Netherlands	A and B-wood	non-impregnated, excluding packaging
	C wood	wood treated with copper / chromium / arsenic
United Kingdom	Grade A	Clean, untreated wood (pre-consumer, untreated packaging)
	Grade B	Business waste wood; treated, non-hazardous
	Grade C	Municipal waste wood; treated, non-hazardous
	Grade D	Hazardous waste wood; treated, hazardous
Spain	Clean, untreated wood	Can be reused or recycled directly
	Construction and demolition wood	Includes planks, frames, and construction debris
	Packaging wood	Such as pallets and crates
	Furniture wood	Can be recycled into new wood products
	Wood treated with hazardous chemicals (such as copper, chromium, arsenic or creosote)	not suitable for recycling

A very general incentive to increase the use of recycled wood in construction products can directly or indirectly be concluded from action plans such as the UK's 25 Year Plan to Improve the Environment, which encourages a more efficient use of resources and minimisation of waste by promoting reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling. Very similar to this is the Danish National Strategy for Sustainable Construction that strives for more climate-friendly building and construction as well as resource-efficient buildings. On the other hand, there are also much more specific incentives in the Danish and Dutch building regulations. Where the Dutch authorities set continuously stricter requirements to the environmental impact of new-built homes and office buildings with an area larger than 100 m², the Danish regulation now allows to count recycled construction material with 0 kg towards the CO₂ calculation in Life Cycle Assessments.

The regulation analysis did not identify any explicit barriers on the level of building regulations that prevent the re-use or use of construction products manufactured from recycled material. This, however, is not certain proof that they do not exist.

4.2 Placing construction products on the market

Whether a construction product is manufactured within one of the Member States of the European Union or in any other country worldwide, certain requirements must be met before the product can be placed on the European market.

“Placing on the market” is defined as making a construction product available on the European internal market for the first time. This can either be done for further distribution of the product or as a direct supply for a specific construction activity. It is not relevant if the product is provided free of charge or in return for payment. In the context of “placing on the market” of construction products, it is also essential that the product in question is supplied for the purpose of permanent incorporation into construction works. Materials supplied as input for further manufacturing processes of a construction product may not be considered “placed on the market” in the sense of the definition. In the context of WOODCIRCLES, this would mean that if the urban sawmill produced lamellae as input material for CLT, these lamellae would not be considered placed on the market by selling them to the CLT manufacturer. Only the CLT manufacturer would place the finished CLT product on the market.

The rules that must be followed to place a construction product covered by a harmonised technical specification on the market are defined by the Construction Products Regulation and aim to provide relevant information about the performance of the product. That information is provided in the form of a Declaration of Performance, either referring to a harmonised EN-standard or to a European Technical Assessment (ETA) based on a European Assessment Declaration (EAD).

If a construction product is not covered by a harmonised technical specification, placing it on the market will be subject to the national provisions of the country in which it is made available. In that context, the Member States are required to apply the Mutual recognition principle and as far as possible accept documentation established under the rules of other Member States.

The different conditions for placing products on the market are shown in the decision tree below (Figure 2). A more detailed explanation of the terms used and the paths available is given in the following sub-chapters.

Figure 2: DECISION TREE ON HOW TO PLACE A CONSTRUCTION PRODUCT ON THE MARKET

4.2.1 Construction Products Regulation

The Construction Products Regulation¹ (CPR) defines the harmonised conditions for the placing on the market of construction products by establishing a common technical language for providing information on the performance of the products. That information enables the users to compare product performances across the market and make informed decisions on their choices. It is important to note that products under the CPR must be marketed with a declaration of performance (DOP), though, the manufacturer is free to decide for which essential characteristics a performance is declared. An example would be the declaration of the strength value of a CLT plate/element for load-carrying purposes. However, the DOP does not guarantee that a product fulfils the requirements for any possible construction. The declared performance provides information that users may apply to assess whether a product fulfils the expectations set for a specific construction project.

The current CPR (Regulation (EU) No 305/2011) has been in the process of revision and a new CPR is expected to be adopted in the course of 2024. The revised regulation will additionally include provisions for the declaration of performance regarding the environmental sustainability of a product.

4.2.2 European Standard (EN-standard)

A European standard is the result of an established consensus between all Member organisations of the European Standardisation organisation on rules and definitions pertaining to a specific product. It aims to remove barriers in trade and is implemented as a national standard in all Member States.

European standards typically provide a list of essential characteristics (i.e. bending strength, density) that may be declared for a product as well as relevant test methods for the determination of said characteristics. The standards offer the possibility to be applied but it is not mandatory to do so. Other available standards covering the same type of product can be used as well.

4.2.3 Harmonised European Standard (hEN-standard)

A harmonised European standard for construction products is drawn up in accordance with a request issued by the European Commission and is published in the Official Journal of the European Union³ (OJEU). It is binding for economic operators making construction products available on the market that are covered by the standard. Member States are required to define their national requirements on the harmonised standards, so that fulfilment of national requirements can be assessed on the basis of a declaration of performance referring to the harmonised standards.

4.2.4 European Assessment Document (EAD) and European Technical Assessment (ETA)

A European Assessment Document (EAD) is developed by the European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA) when a manufacturer requests a European technical assessment (ETA) for a construction product that is not covered, or not fully covered, by a harmonised standard. The developed EAD is the harmonised technical specification of a construction product covered by it. It provides next to a general description of the product, the methods and criteria for assessing the product performance in relation to the essential characteristics that have been identified as relevant and requested by the manufacturer(s).

The European Technical Assessment (ETA) of a construction product provides information on the performance assessment conducted. Thereby, an ETA offers an alternative path to CE marking of a construction product. ETAs are issued by Technical Assessment Bodies (TAB).

4.2.5 CE marking

CE marking of a product makes the product eligible to be traded within the entire European market without restrictions. At the same time, it ensures that the performances declared for a construction product are comparable to other products of that kind because the assessment methods used for the declaration of the performance are harmonised. The performances that must be declared at a minimum may be defined by delegated acts issued by the European Commission.

However, CE marking is only mandatory for construction products covered by harmonised standards. Products not covered by harmonised standards would be subjects to the national rules of the country where it is made available. In this case, all relevant information obligatory under law in the specific country must be identified and provided.

4.2.6 Other standards

Individual (national) standards on Member State level may exist where there are no European standards available to cover a product. Further sources offering testing methods to determine product performances and other specifications may be ISO standards or standards published by countries or organisations located outside of the European Union.

4.2.7 Mutual recognition principle

The Mutual recognition principle⁴ (Regulation (EU) 2019/515) allows for products that are lawfully marketed in one Member State to also be marketable in all other Member States. It prohibits the application of national rules that would exclude a product from market access unless restrictions are justified on the grounds of protecting the health and life of humans, animals or plants as well as protecting national treasures possessing artistic, historic, or archaeological value and protecting industrial and commercial property.

Adhering to this principle it would therefore be possible to market a construction product across all Member States even if it is not CE marked but was placed on the market of one Member State by fulfilling all the country-specific national requirements.

4.3 Placing WOODCIRCLES products on the market

WOODCIRCLES focuses on lamella production for cross-laminated timber (CLT) and glued laminated timber (GLT), as well as fibre insulation products from construction and demolition wood. Therefore, the available possibilities of placing these specific products on the European market were analysed in depth and the summarized result is illustrated below (Figure 3) with a more detailed description relating to each product in the following sub-chapters.

Figure 3: DECISION TREE SHOWING THE POSSIBILITIES FOR CROSSLAMINATED TIMBER, GLUED LAMINATED TIMBER, FINGER-JOINTED LAMELLA, AND FIBRE INSULATION TO BE PLACED ON THE MARKET.

4.3.1 Fibre insulation mats

Fibre insulation mats are an example for the easiest path to place a product on the market. The existing standard *EN 13171:2012+A1:2015 (E), Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products – Specification* is harmonised, and recycled material is not excluded from the scope.

Due to this coverage of the product by the harmonised standard it must be applied for CE marking of the mats.

4.3.2 Fibre insulation, loose

In contrast to fibre insulation mats, an EN standard on loose fibre insulation products does not exist. However, there are two EADs available that both include the use of untreated chipped wood in their scope (EAD 040138-00-1201 In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres, EAD 041125-00-1201 In-situ loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres to be used in floor constructions without additional load-bearing structures). Thus, if the product properties are covered by all the EAD's scope requirements and the EAD includes all identified essential characteristics required for the intended use, CE marking and placing on the market can be achieved by a European Technical Assessment (ETA). If the available EADs do not cover all relevant essential characteristics or the product does not fit into the scope, a new version or variant EAD can be drawn up based on the presented product specifications. Alternatively, the product can be placed on the market under national rules.

4.3.3 Cross-laminated timber

The standard available for CLT products (EN 16351:2021, Timber structures - Cross laminated timber – Requirements) allows for the layers of the product to be made from different wood species that are included in the scope. However, the scope specifically excludes the use of re-used timber. In addition, the standard is not harmonised, so CE marking of the product is not possible on the basis of EN 16351. This leaves two options.

The first option is to apply for an ETA. There is currently one EAD that the ETA could be based on (EAD 130005-00-0304 Solid wood slab element to be used as a structural element in buildings), though the scope is limited to the use of European spruce (*Picea abies*) or equivalent softwoods. The other existing EAD specifically excludes the use of recycled wood (EAD 130013-00-0304 Solid wood slab element to be used as a structural element in buildings - element of timber boards jointed by dovetail connections). If both EADs do not cover the WOODCIRCLES CLT product, the application for the ETA will trigger the process of drawing up a new EAD, or a new version of one of the existing EADs, that covers the product and the essential characteristics for which the manufacturer wishes to declare the performance.

The second option includes the identification of the regulatory requirements of the country of destination as well as the relevant methods and their respective standards applicable to document the conformity with these requirements.

In relation to strength testing of the input material, the CLT product standard *EN 16351:2021* references the harmonised product standard *EN 14081-1:2005+A1:2011, Timber structures - Strength graded structural timber with rectangular cross section - Part 1: General Requirements*. The described method requires that the wood species of the timber that is graded is known. It also, in turn, references *EN 1912:2012 Structural Timber - Strength classes - Assignment of visual grades and species* as the basis for strength grading. This includes not only the requirement that the species must be known but also knowledge of the original source (growth area) of the timber, e.g. France, Germany, Spain or Central, Northern and Eastern Europe, which makes it nearly impossible to apply to timber sourced from demolition sites. The same can be stated for machine grading timber according to the referenced standard *EN 14081-2:2018 Timber structures - Strength graded structural timber with rectangular cross*

section - Part 2: Machine grading; additional requirements for initial type testing because the developed grading protocols also require knowledge about the origin of the timber and the wood species. In addition, these protocols are always based on the experience gained from virgin wood.

At last, this directs the search for relevant test methods to the content of other EADs and EN standards as well as ISO standards or national standards. If relevant methods for testing can be identified in these, they can be applied to determine the product performances required, so that placing on the market in line with national rules becomes possible.

4.3.4 Glued laminated timber

For glued laminated timber products there is a harmonised standard available (EN 14080:2013 Timber structures - Glued laminated timber and glued solid timber – Requirements), its scope covering a list of softwood species as well as poplar wood. However, for the applicability of the standard it is also required that the product is produced from only one wood species throughout which makes it unlikely to be functional for GLT produced from demolition wood. In addition, the GLT product standard also directly references *EN 14081-1:2005+A1:2011, Timber structures - Strength graded structural timber with rectangular cross section - Part 1: General Requirements* which leads to the same situation regarding the strength grading of the lamellae as described in the chapter on CLT.

Thus, the inapplicability of the harmonised GLT product standard points to the request of an ETA for WOODCIRCLES GLT products, where the developed EAD includes a mix of wood species as input and allows for them to be of unknown origin and recycling quality. It is currently not possible to use any existing EADs for WOODCIRCLES GLT products (EAD 130320-00-0304 Glued laminated timber made of solid hardwood, EAD 130484-00-0304 Tension proof loaded structural finger jointed solid timber which may be processed to glued laminated timber and glued solid timber or EAD 130197-00-0304 Glued laminated timber made of steam-cured solid timber with rectangular cross section – Softwood) because their scope is either limited to hardwoods and excludes recycling wood or is very specific on the softwood species or the pre-treatment. Additionally, all existing EADs include strength grading in accordance with *EN 14081-1:2005+A1:2011* which poses a barrier just as it does in the application of the harmonised standard. Therefore, another method would be necessary for assessing the structural behaviour of GLT based on recycled wood.

4.3.5 Finger-jointed lamella

Finger-jointed timber as construction product for use in buildings and bridges is at a first glance covered by the harmonised standard *EN 15497:2014 Structural finger jointed solid timber - Performance requirements and minimum production requirements*. However, the standard's scope is limited to specific softwood species and poplar wood and most importantly requires that jointed timber sections are made from the same wood species. This, as well as the referenced standard for strength classes (EN 338:2016 Structural timber - Strength classes) which, in turn, refers to *EN 14081-1:2005+A1:2011, Timber structures - Strength graded structural timber with rectangular cross section - Part 1: General Requirements* requiring wood species and origins to be known, prevent the harmonised product standard to be directly applicable to any finger-jointed lamellae produced in WOODCIRCLES.

Therefore, it is an option to achieve CE marking of the product and thus placing on the market by applying for an ETA based on the product specifications. A new EAD will most likely have to be developed for this purpose, since the ones in existence at this point in time (EAD 130089-00-0304 Structural wet and/or

cold glued finger jointed solid timber, EAD 130166-00-0304 Strength graded structural timber - Steam cured solid timber with rectangular cross section which may be finger jointed or not – softwood, EAD 130484-00-0304 Tension proof loaded structural finger jointed solid timber which may be processed to glued laminated timber and glued solid timber) do not cover any product that includes recycled wood and require strength grading based on the aforementioned standard *EN 14081-1:2005+A1:2011*.

5. Conclusions

The regulation analysis along the WOODCIRCLES value chain, has identified regulations, laws, standards, guidance and other documents that indicate the possibilities and challenges within this project and highlights where change might be needed.

Overall, most of the existing regulations and directives include the aim to increase sustainability by increasing re-use and recycling of materials. In line with this, on the national level of building regulations, specific incentives could be identified while there do not seem to be any barriers. The challenge rather lies within the sourcing of the input material and the qualification of the construction product for placement on the market.

Rules on demolition practices vary from country to country, from being very precise to providing a wide framework, the only specific common goal across Member States being the separation of hazardous and non-hazardous materials at the demolition site.

Each country also defines their own rules and guidelines for the sorting and handling of waste wood. While hazardous wood is always kept separately, the categories established for further sorting of non-hazardous wood waste vary, even down to a local level. Thus, reliable information must be obtained directly from specific collection sites of interest.

Placing the developed construction products on the market could be considered as the most challenging step in the process as the available harmonised standards are not compatible with the use of recycled wood. This does not in any case exclude the possibility of placing these products on the market, but it increases the workload and time needed to achieve market access either by CE marking or other means. However, as this situation is not unknown, there have already been efforts in the development of new methods, and new standards are currently under hearing.

References

- 1 Construction Product Regulation (EU) No 305/2011
(REGULATION (EU) No 305/2011 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC)
https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/european-standards/harmonised-standards/construction-products-cpdcp_en
- 2 NS 3691-1 Evaluering av returtre – Del 1: Terminologi og generelle regler, NS 3691-2 Evaluering av returtre – Del 2: Urenheter, NS 3691-1 Evaluering av returtre - Del 3: Visuell styrkesortering

<https://www.treteknisk.no/aktuelt/nye-standarder-for-evaluering-av-returtre>

- 3 Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU) related to Regulation (EU) No 305/2011
[https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52018XC0309\(09\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52018XC0309(09))
- 4 REGULATION (EU) 2019/515 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 19 March 2019 on the mutual recognition of goods lawfully marketed in another Member State and repealing Regulation (EC) No 764/2008
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019R0515>